

Tetrahydroindolizine-3,8 (2H, 5H)-dione and Related 3-Piperidones

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Tetrahydroindolizine-3,8 (2H, 5H)-dione (III) has been synthesized from methyl 5-oxo-2-pyrrolidine carboxylate (VIII). Its structure has been assigned on the basis of spectroscopic data and an independent synthesis of its ethylene ketal (XII) from N-acetyl-3-piperidone (IV). The IR and ^1H NMR spectra of III have been compared with the corresponding spectra of IV, N-ethoxycarbonyl-3-piperidone (V), N-ethyl-3-piperidone (VI) and N-benzyl-3-piperidone (VII). The position of the ketonic carbonyl-stretching band in the IR spectra of both the N-acyl- and N-alkyl-3-piperidones has been found to be at $\sim 5.80 \mu$ and this observation has provided a basis for the interpretation of the remarkably short wavelength of the ketonic carbonyl-stretching band of the alkaloid haplophytine (I). In their ^1H NMR spectra the N-acyl compounds show large downfield shifts of the C-2 and C-6 proton signals relative to their N-alkyl counterparts. Compounds IV and III have been found to undergo ready autoxidation involving oxidative cleavage of the C-2-C-3 bond of the 3-piperidone system to give N-formyl-4-acetamidobutyric acid (XXI) and N-(3-carboxypropyl) succinimide (XXII), respectively.

In the course of the determination of the structure of the alkaloid haplophytine(I) several unusual spectroscopic features have been encountered¹. In order to elucidate the origin of these we have undertaken a study of model compounds that contain certain of the structural units of haplophytine. We describe here the synthesis of tetrahydroindolizine-3,8 (2H,5H)-dione(III), whose structural features are incorporated into the canthiphytine moiety (II) of haplophytine, and compare its properties with those of the related 3-piperidones (IV-VII).

This gave a positive ferric chloride test for the presence of an enol and showed in its IR spectrum a low-to-medium intensity band in the $3\text{-}4.5 \mu$ region characteristic of enolic hydroxyl stretch. In addition, complex absorption in the 5.94μ region can be assigned to overlap of bands of the lactam and ester groups of X, while a band at 6.17μ is assignable to the enolic ethylenic bond. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the product provided further evidence for the structural assignment in that it showed a sharp one-proton singlet at δ 12.15 that is absent after treatment with deuterium oxide; this can be assigned to the enolic proton of X. A broad two proton multiplet in the region δ 4.0-4.4 is assignable to the C-8a and one of the C-5 hydrogens (molecular models show that one of the C-5 hydrogens is held in the plane of the lactam carbonyl group)⁴.

Treatment of X with hot 6N hydrochloric acid resulted in its hydrolysis and decarboxylation to give III. This could be obtained in crystalline form by sublimation, but the crystals softened rapidly upon exposure to air. This rapid autoxidation (*vide infra*) prevented the obtention of reliable elemental analytical data, however the composition of the product was established by high resolution mass spectrometry. Its IR spectrum confirmed the presence of ketone (5.79μ) and five-membered lactam (5.94μ) groups. Its ^1H NMR spectrum, like that of X, showed a two-proton multiplet in the region δ 3.94-4.4 that can be assigned to the C-8a hydrogen and to one of the C-5 hydrogens. Its ^{13}C NMR spectrum is also in accord with the structural assignment.*

A small amount of III was also isolated when the aqueous phase from the work-up of the Dieckmann cyclization reaction of IX was subjected to continuous extraction with dichloromethane. This might have

Methyl 5-oxo-2-pyrrolidinecarboxylate(VIII)² was N-alkylated with ethyl 4-bromobutyrate and sodium iodide to give IX *via* formation of its sodio derivative with sodium hydride in dimethylformamide³. Dieckmann cyclization of IX with methanolic sodium methoxide gave a product that is assigned structure X.

* The ^{13}C NMR spectra of III and related compounds will be discussed elsewhere

arisen *via* hydrolysis of X under the mild acidic conditions of the aqueous work-up; however, treatment of X with 0.5*N* hydrochloric acid at room temperature failed to effect its hydrolysis. An alternative source of III is the non-enolizable β -keto ester (XI), which may have undergone cleavage by sodium methoxide to give III and dimethyl carbonate (the enolate anion of III may be stabilized by the adjacent amide group⁵).

The elemental composition of III was corroborated by its conversion to the corresponding ethylene ketal (XII), whose enhanced stability permitted the obtention of a satisfactory elemental analysis, and the structural assignment was confirmed by an independent synthesis of XII. *N*-Acetyl-3-piperidone (IV) was prepared by a modification of the method of Masamune and coworkers⁶. Like III it is unstable in air, but gives an ethylene ketal (XIII), that does not undergo ready autoxidation. Compound IV was converted to XV *via* conversion to the enamine (XIV) and reaction of this with ethyl acrylate, again by a modification of the procedure of Masamune and coworkers⁶. The spectroscopic data for XV show that it, like IV^{6,7} and XIII, exists in solution as two rotational isomers about the N-CO bond. This compound resembled III and IV in its sensitivity to autoxidation. Ketalization of XV with ethylene glycol was very slow and in order to keep the reaction time within reasonable limits it was necessary

to use a greater than catalytic amount of *p*-toluene-sulfonic acid. This resulted in some alcoholysis of the ethyl ester by ethylene glycol and the product obtained was a mixture of the ketals (XVI and XVII), as evidenced by its ¹H NMR spectrum. Treatment of this mixture with concentrated methanolic sodium methoxide gave XII in low yield.

Of the 3-piperidones (IV-VII), the preparation of IV has already been alluded to; VI and VII were prepared from their commercially available hydrochlorides, while V was prepared by treatment of VII with ethyl chloroformate⁸. The solution (CHCl₃) IR and ¹H NMR spectra of these compounds and of compounds III and XV are compared in the Table. The IR bands of the ketonic carbonyl groups fall in the range 5.79-5.81 μ , with III at the lower end of this range. This is of particular relevance in relation to the position of the ketonic carbonyl band of the canthiphytine moiety (II) of haplophytine. This is superimposed on the lactonic carbonyl band of the aspidophytine moiety and occurs at the extraordinarily short wavelength of 5.73 μ . The present results suggest that this shift of 0.12 μ relative to cyclohexanone (5.85 μ) can largely be accounted for in terms of the circumstance that the

TABLE—INFRARED AND PROTON MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTRA OF 3-PIPERIDONES.

Compound	CHCl ₃ , λ_{max}, μ	H ₂ CDCl ₃
(III)	5.79, 5.94	1.6-2.7 (m, 8H), 2.85-3.4 (m, 1H), 3.9-4.4 (m, 2H)
(IV)	5.80, 6.10	1.7-2.3 (m, ^a 5H), 2.4-2.7 (m, 2H), 3.73 (br t, <i>J</i> =6Hz, 2H) 4.08 (s, 0.5H) 4.17 (s, 1.5H)
(V)	5.80, 5.91	1.29 (t, <i>J</i> =7Hz, 3H), 1.8-2.3 (m, 2H), 2.3-2.7 (m, 2H), 3.66 (t, <i>J</i> =6Hz, 2H), 4.07 (s, 2H), 4.18 (q, <i>J</i> =7Hz, 2H)
(VI)	5.80	1.08 (t, <i>J</i> =7Hz, 3H), 1.7-2.2 (m, 2H), 2.2-2.8 (m, 6H), 3.00 (s, 2H)
(VII)	5.80	1.7-2.1 (m, 2H), 2.15-2.5 (m, 2H), 2.5-2.7 (m, 2H), 2.97 (s, 2H), 3.55 (s, 2H), 7.3 (s, 5H)
(XV)	5.81, 6.10	1.25 (t, <i>J</i> =7.5 Hz, 3H), 1.8-2.75 (m, ^b 11H), 3.2-4.4 (m, ^c 4.25H), 5.02 (br t, <i>J</i> =7 Hz, 0.75 H)

^a With superimposed singlet at δ 2.14.

^b With superimposed singlet at δ 2.18.

^c With superimposed quartet (*J*=7.5 Hz) at δ 4.16.

carbonyl group of II is incorporated into both a system of type III and an *N*-alkyl-3-piperidone system, each of which has been shown to bring about a shift of the carbonyl band of *ca.* 0.05 μ to shorter wavelength relative to cyclohexanone. Although these effects would not be expected to be fully additive, a further factor can be invoked to account for the observed shift of 0.12 μ for II, *viz.*, the incorporation of the carbonyl group at

the C-9 position of a benzodiazabicyclo [3.3.1]nonene system. Thus, it has been reported that neat XVIII absorbs at $5.76 \mu^9$, 0.07μ to shorter wavelength than neat N-methyl-3-piperidone (XIX) (5.83μ)¹⁰.

Although the position of the carbonyl-stretching bands of the N-acyl-3-piperidones (IV and V) are identical to those of the N-alkyl-3-piperidones (VI and VII), the ¹H NMR shifts of the C-2 and C-6 methylene protons in the two types of derivative are, as expected, markedly different. In the case of the N-acyl compounds these protons give rise to signals at $\delta \sim 4.1$ and $\delta \sim 3.7$, respectively, whereas the corresponding values for the N-alkyl compounds are ~ 3.0 and ~ 2.6 . Similar, but much smaller effects may be noted for the C-4 and C-5 methylene protons. Although the spectra of III and XV were not fully analyzed because of their greater complexity, they nevertheless can be recognized as resembling those of the N-acyl compounds (IV and V). As noted previously the ¹H NMR spectra of the N-acyl compounds (IV and XV) show the presence of two rotational isomers about the N-CO bond; in both cases the isomer ratio is $\sim 3:1$. It is of interest that in neither case is there any differentiation of the isomers in the carbonyl-stretching regions of the IR spectra, while in the case of XIII the ethylene ketal of IV, rotational isomerism is evidenced by both its ¹H NMR and its IR spectra (see Experimental). A further point of interest is the lack of evidence for rotational isomerism in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the N-carboethoxy derivative (V). A similar difference between the N-acetyl and N-carboethoxy derivatives has been reported in the 4-piperidone series⁷.

Finally, we consider the ready autoxidation of several of the 3-piperidones prepared in this work. Samples of N-acetyl-3-piperidone (IV) stored at -20° for several months partially solidified. The solid material was found to contain two components. One of these was obtained in pure form and was shown by its spectra and melting point to be 4-acetamidobutyric acid (XX). The major component was not completely purified, but its spectra, source, and isolation in admixture with XX clearly indicate that it is XXI, the N-formyl derivative of XX. Related observations were made in the case of III, which also was converted to a carboxylic acid on exposure to air. Methylation of the crude autoxidation product with diazomethane permitted the isolation of a crystalline solid that was shown to be N-[(3-methoxycarbonyl)propyl] succinimide (XXII) on the basis of its spectra and comparison with an authentic sample prepared from succinimide and ethyl 4-bromo-butylate in the presence of methanolic sodium methoxide. The corresponding autoxidation product from III must therefore be the acid XXIII.

It appears likely that XXI and XXIII arise *via* autoxidation of the parent α -carboxamido ketones to their α -hydroperoxy derivatives, e.g. XXIV, a process that should be facilitated by stabilization of the radical intermediates by the adjacent carboxamido and carbonyl groups¹¹. Cleavage of the α -hydroperoxy ketones could then occur *via* the tautomeric hydroxy-1,2-dioxetanes, e.g. XXV, as previously proposed to account for the formation of mesitoic acid and acetone on autoxidation of isopropyl mesityl ketone¹². The further conversion of XXI to XX could involve either further autoxidation followed by decarboxylation or hydrolytic cleavage.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Infrared and NMR spectra were recorded in CHCl_3 and CDCl_3 , respectively, unless otherwise indicated. Preparative TLC was carried out on $20 \times 20 \times 0.5$ mm silica gel "G" plates containing a fluorescent indicator; iodine or UV visualization, where applicable, was used. The bands were extracted with methanol and the residues obtained after filtration and evaporation were stirred in CH_2Cl_2 ; filtration and evaporation gave the products. Unless indicated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 .

Methyl N-[3-(Ethoxycarbonyl)propyl]-5-oxo-2-pyrrolidinecarboxylate (IX)—Dry ether (5 ml) was added by syringe to NaH (59% in mineral oil; 635 mg, 15.6 mmol) under N_2 in a two-necked r.b. flask fitted with a condenser and rubber septum. The mixture was stirred for 30 sec and allowed to settle; the ether was removed by decantation using a syringe. The procedure was repeated twice and the last traces of ether were driven off with a stream of N_2 (using another needle through the septum for an escape valve). Dry DMF (distilled at water aspirator pressure from calcium hydride; 25 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred and cooled in an ice bath. A solution of NaI (50 mg, 0.33 mmol) in DMF (5 ml) was added by syringe followed by a solution of lactam (VIII; 2.18 g, 14.8 mmol) in DMF (13 ml), which was added dropwise during 5 min. Slow effervescence was observed and the ice bath was removed. After 50 min the evolution of gas had subsided, and the mixture was cooled in an

ice bath and ethyl 4-bromobutyrate (2.88 g, 14.8 mmol) was added by syringe. The mixture was warmed to 50° and after 2 hr an opaque yellow solution resulted. After 110 hr the brown-green solution was evaporated. The residue was diluted with ice-cold water (30 ml) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 15 ml). The organic extracts were washed with water (10 ml), dried, and evaporated to leave 3.2 g of a yellow-green oil. The combined aqueous phases were saturated with NaCl and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. Drying and evaporation gave an additional oil (0.5g). The combined oils were molecularly distilled at 150° (0.005 mm) to give 2.2 g of an oil. This was chromatographed on a column of silica gel (40:1) with 1% methanol in CHCl₃ as eluent. Compound IX was obtained as the first major fraction eluted (940 mg, 25%). This was molecularly distilled at 112° (0.005 mm) prior to analysis; λ_{max} 5.75, 5.78 (sh), 5.93 μ ; $H\delta$ 1.23 (t, $J=7$ Hz, 3H), 1.6-2.7 (m, 8H), 2.8-3.85 (m with superimposed s at 3.76. 5H), 4.0-4.4 (m with superimposed q at 4.12, $J=7$ Hz, 3H); m/e 257 (50). (Found: C, 55.85; H, 7.51; N, 5.35. C₁₂H₁₉NO₂ requires C, 56.02; H, 7.44; N, 5.44).

After IX was eluted, the column was stripped with methanol (200 ml) to give VIII (1.12 g). This material, combined with 176 mg obtained after mol. distillation of the residue from continuous extraction of the aqueous phase, represents a 68% recovery of starting material.

Keto Ester (X)—A solution of diester (IX; 528 mg, 2.05 mmol) in dry methanol (3 ml) was added by syringe to methanolic NaOMe (prepared by adding freshly cut Na (55 mg, 2.4 mmol) to 1.2 ml of dry CH₃OH) under N₂ and the pale yellow solution was boiled under reflux. After 20 hr the solvent was evaporated, the brown residue was dissolved in water (12 ml), and the solution was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 10 ml). The organic extracts were dried and evaporated to leave a tan oil (38 mg) which solidified after scratching. The aqueous phase was acidified to pH 5 with aqueous 2 N HCl and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic extracts were dried and evaporated to leave a light brown oil (173 mg). The combined products represent a 49% yield of crude keto ester (X). This was molecularly distilled at 58° (0.005 mm) to give a tan solid which was crystallized from ether m.p. 82-84°; λ_{max} 3-4.5(m), 5.90, 5.96, 6.00 (sh), 6.27 μ ; $H\delta$ 1.6-3.0 (m, 7H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 4.0-4.4 (m, 2H), 12.15 (s, 1H; absent after D₂O treatment). This compound decomposed during an attempted sublimation (<100°, 0.005 mm). The aqueous phase was saturated with NaCl and extracted continuously for 12 hr. Drying and evaporation gave a brown oil (100 mg) which was molecularly distilled to give pale yellow oil (28 mg). Redistillation gave a crystalline solid which softened rapidly after exposure to air and was identified as ketone (III) by comparison of its IR spectrum with that of an authentic sample obtained from acid hydrolysis of keto ester (X) (*vide infra*).

Tetrahydroindolizine-3, 8 (2H, 5H)-dione (II)—A solution of keto ester (X; 59 mg, 0.28 mmol) in aqueous 6 N HCl (5 ml) was heated under N₂ to 82°.

After 1.5 hr the solution was extracted continuously for 24 hr with CH₂Cl₂. The organic extracts were dried and evaporated leaving a tan oil (36 mg, 84%). Sublimation at 62° (0.005 mm) gave crystals which softened rapidly after exposure to air and whose IR spectrum was identical with that of the oil obtained above; extraction of the aqueous phase for a further 24 hr gave no additional product. The IR and ¹H NMR spectra of this compound are listed in the Table; $C\delta$ (s f. o. r. d.) 18.7 (t), 23.9 (t), 30.0 (t), 39.0 (t), 39.1 (t), 64.0 (d), 173.5 (s), 205.8 (s); m/e 153.0789 (M^+ 153.0789).

N-Acetyl-3-piperidone (IV)—A stirred solution of N-acetyl-1, 4, 5, 6-tetrahydropyridine (containing ~10% N-acetyl-piperidine; 6.0 g, 43.2 mmol),^{1,3} was cooled at -20° in an acetone-dry ice bath and a solution of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (85%, 10.90 g, 53.7 mmol) in dry ether (60 ml) was added during 3 min. The bath was removed and the contents of the reaction flask were allowed to warm to room temp. After 30 min at room temp. a negative test for active oxidant (with KI starch test paper moistened with 2N aq. HOAc) indicated completion of the reaction. The solution was divided into two equal portions and the solvents were evaporated from each (<40°), leaving sticky, white masses. The flasks (100 ml, 24/40 wide mouthed) containing the residues were fitted with condensers attached to a vacuum line and were slowly heated in an oil bath at 0.25 mm. At 110° decomposition was evident as solid and adhering liquid began to collect above the oil level. The flasks, almost submerged in the bath, were kept at 150° for 75 min and then cooled at room temp and purged with N₂. The solid that had collected on the condenser was washed down with ether (30 ml each). The combined ethereal solutions were extracted with water (1 × 20 and 3 × 10 ml) and the aqueous extracts were back-washed with ether (2 × 30 ml). The combined ethereal layers were dried and evaporated to yield a white mass with the strong odour of the starting enamide. The combined aqueous extracts were saturated with NaCl and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (4 × 10 ml). These extracts were dried and evaporated to leave an oil (3.39 g). The aqueous phase was extracted continuously with CH₂Cl₂ for 13 and then 24 hr affording a further 773 and 391 mg of product, respectively. The combined CH₂Cl₂ extracts were molecularly distilled at 65° (0.005 mm) to give 2.64 g of distillate. The distillation residue was extracted with hot ether (4 × 25 ml); the extract was separated by decantation and the ether was evaporated to give an additional 615 mg of product. The combined products, after distillation, represented a 53% yield of IV; its spectra are listed in the Table.

N-Acetyl-3-piperidone Ethylene Ketal (XIII)—N-Acetyl-3-piperidone (2.27 g, 16.1 mmol) in benzene (65 ml) was added to *p*-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (0.5 g, 2.6 mmol) and ethylene glycol (4.96 g, 80 mmol) under N₂ in a 100 ml r.b. flask. The flask was fitted with a Dean-Stark trap and the mixture was stirred and boiled at reflux to allow the separation of water. After 108 hr the benzene was evaporated and residual ethylene glycol was removed *in vacuo* (0.005 mm).

The residue was taken up in CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml) and washed with aqueous 10% NaHCO_3 (15 ml). The aqueous phase was extracted with additional CH_2Cl_2 (2×10 ml) and the combined organic phases was dried and evaporated to yield 2.73 g of an oil which crystallized on trituration. After saturation with NaCl , the aqueous phase was extracted continuously with CH_2Cl_2 yielding an additional 0.19 g of oil. Sublimation at 45° (0.005 mm) gave crystals, mp $61-62.5^\circ$, in an overall yield of 81%. Recrystallization from ether yielded thick, clear needles, mp $63.5-65^\circ$; λ_{max} 6.07, 6.12 μ ; ^1H δ 1.5-1.9 (m, 4H), 2.05 (sh) and 2.07 (s) (3H), 3.2-3.7 (m, 4H), 3.98 (s, 4H); m/e 185 (12). (Found: C, 58.44; H, 8.24; N, 7.60. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 58.36; H, 8.16; N, 7.56).

Acid Hydrolysis of Ketal (XIII). Regeneration of *N*-Acetyl-3-piperidone (IV)—A solution of ketal (XIII; 16.8 mg, 0.09 mmol) in aqueous 2 *N* HCl (2 ml, 4 mmol) was heated under N_2 at 45° . After 6 hr the solution was saturated with NaCl and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×10 ml). The extracts were dried and evaporated to give 8 mg (67%) of ketone (IV), identified by comparison of its ^1H NMR spectrum with that of an authentic sample.

Ethyl 3-[2-(*N*-Acetyl-3-oxopiperidyl)] propionate (XV)—The preparation of this compound from (IV) essentially followed the procedure of Masamune *et al.*⁶. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the crude enamine (XIV) revealed the presence of benzene and pyrrolidine. The hydrolysis of the product from XIV and ethyl acrylate was performed in a flask rather than a sealed tube. A partial separation of the products was effected by extraction of the hydrolysis residue with ethyl acetate. Column chromatography of the ethyl acetate-soluble portion on silica gel (30:1) with ethyl acetate as eluent afforded XV in 76% yield as the first major component eluted. This oil was stored at -20° under a dry N_2 atmosphere and was molecularly distilled at 110° (0.005 mm) before use: its spectra are listed in the Table; m/e 241 (29).

Compounds (XVI) and (XVII)—Ketone (XV; 368 mg, 1.53 mmol) in benzene (40 ml) was added to *p*-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (60 mg, 0.32 mmol) and ethylene glycol (1.0 ml, 17.7 mmol) under N_2 in a 50-ml r.b. flask. The flask was fitted with a Dean-Stark trap and the mixture was boiled at reflux. After 61 hr the mixture was cooled to room temp. and aq 10% Na_2CO_3 (10 ml) was added. After separation of the organic phase the aqueous phase was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×10 ml). The combined organic extracts were dried (K_2CO_3) and evaporated to leave a mixture of XVI and XVII as an oil (0.5g).

Tetrahydroindolizine-3,8 (2*H*,5*H*)-dione Ethylene Ketal (XII).

(a) *From (XVI) and (XVII)*—A solution of the mixture of ketals (XVI and XVII; 240 mg, ~ 0.8 mmol) in dry methanol (2.5 ml) was added by syringe to methanolic NaOMe [prepared by adding freshly cut Na (246 mg, 10.5 mmol) to dry CH_3OH (2.5 ml) and heat-

ing until H_2 evolution ceased] under N_2 in a thick-walled reaction tube. The tube was sealed and placed in an oven. After 67 hr at 147° the tube was cooled and opened, the solvent was evaporated, aqueous 0.5 *N* HCl (20 ml, 10 mmol) was added, and the orange-yellow solution was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (5×6 ml). These extracts were dried and evaporated leaving a brown-orange residue (36 mg). TLC on silica gel with ethyl acetate as eluent followed by extraction of the band with R_f 0.2 gave ketal (XII) as a pale yellow oil (17 mg, $\sim 11\%$): the IR and ^1H NMR spectra of this compound were identical to those of the sample obtained by method (b) below.

(b) *From III*—Ketone (III; 48 mg, 0.31 mmol) in benzene (20 ml) was added to *p*-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (35 mg, 0.18 mmol) and ethylene glycol (40 mg, 7.4 mmol) under N_2 in a 25-ml r.b. flask fitted with a Dean-Stark trap and the mixture was stirred and boiled to allow the separation of water. After 72 hr the benzene was evaporated. The residue was taken up in aqueous 10% NaHCO_3 and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×10 ml). The extracts were dried and evaporated leaving a yellow liquid. Mol. distillation at 65° (0.005 mm) gave a pale yellow oil (59 mg). TLC on silica gel with ethyl acetate as eluent followed by extraction of the band with R_f 0.2 and mol. distillation at 70° (0.005 mm) gave ketal (XII) as an oil (33 mg, 55%); λ_{max} 5.95 μ ; ^1H δ 1.4-2.9 (m, 9H), 3.5-3.75 (m, 1H), 3.9-4.3 (m with superimposed s at 4.00, 5H); m/e 198 (2), 197 (12). (Found: C, 61.15; H, 7.86; N, 6.92. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 60.89; H, 7.67; N, 7.10).

***N*-Ethoxycarbonyl-3-piperidone (V)**—The general method of Wright and Brabander⁹ was modified. A solution of ethyl chloroformate (1.38 g, 12.7 mmol) and *N*-benzyl-3-piperidone (VII; 0.8 g, 4.2 mmol) in benzene (30 ml) under N_2 was boiled at reflux. After 24 hr the solvent was evaporated and the residue on mol. distillation at 75° (0.005 mm) gave an oil (700 mg, 97%); its spectra are listed in the Table. (Found: C, 56.06; H, 7.58; N, 7.82. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 56.13; H, 7.65; N, 8.19).

Oxidation of *N*-Acetyl-3-piperidone (IV) by Air. Isolation of Compounds (XX) and (XXI)—Neat ketone (IV) was stored at -20° under air in a closed flask. After several months yellowing of the oil had occurred and a white solid had separated. Mol. distillation at 43° (0.005 mm) separated residual ketone (IV). The remaining solid was extracted with hot ether and the residue was recrystallized from acetone or chloroform to give 4-acetamidobutyric acid (XX): mp $129-130^\circ$ (lit.¹⁴ mp 129°); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{NaOH}}$ 3-4.5, 3.13, 5.85, 6.24, 6.42 μ ; ^1H δ (CD_3)₂SO [referenced to internal sodium 3-(trimethylsilyl)tetrauteriopropionate] 1.3-2.0 (m with superimposed singlet at 1.85, 5H), 2.1-2.45 (m, 2H), 2.8-3.3 (m, 2H), 7.87 (br s, 1H; absent after D_2O treatment), 11.67 (br s, 1H; absent after D_2O treatment); m/e 146 (9), 145 (20). Evaporation of the ethereal extracts left an oil, which solidified after cooling. This solid was recrystallized from ether and sublimed at 50° (0.005 mm) to give slightly impure XXI; λ_{max} 3-4.2, 5.81, 5.96 μ ; ^1H δ 1.7-2.1 (m, 2H), 2.2-2.6 (m, with

superimposed s at 2.40, 5H), 3.77 (t, $J=7$ Hz, 2H), 9.37 (s, 1H), 10.43 (s, 1H ; absent after D_2O treatment).

(m, 2H), 2.72 (s, 4H), 3.57 (t, $J=7$ Hz, 2H), 3.69 (s, 3H) ; m/e 199 (24). (Found : C, 54.18 ; H, 6.53 ; N, 7.08. $C_9H_{13}NO_4$ requires C, 54.26 ; H, 6.58 ; N, 7.03).

Oxidation of Tetrahydroindolizine-3,8(2H,5H) done (III) by Air. Isolation of Compound (XXII)— Combined samples (131 mg) of neat ketone (III) that had been exposed to air for a minimum of two weeks were dissolved in ice-cold methanol (20 ml) and treated with excess ethereal CH_2N_2 . After 24 hr at room temp. the solvents were evaporated and the residue was distilled molecularly at 92° (0.005 mm) to give a pale yellow oil (40 mg). Extraction of the distillation residue with hot ether (3 x 20 ml) followed by evaporation of the extracts gave an additional 21 mg of oil. TLC of the combined fractions (61 mg) on silica gel with ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (2:1) as eluent followed by extraction of the band with R_f 0.6, after developing two times, gave a pale yellow oil (37 mg). The oil was crystallized from ether to give needles, mp $58-59^\circ$; a mixture with authentic XXII (*vide infra*) had mp $58-59.5^\circ$: the IR spectra of the two samples were superimposable.

N-[3-(Methoxycarbonyl)propyl]succinimide (XXII) : Succinimide (418 mg, 4.21 mmol) was added to methanolic NaOMe [prepared by adding freshly cut Na (97 mg, 4.21 mmol) to 15 ml of dry CH_3OH] under N_2 . After stirring for 5 min at room temp. a solution was obtained. Ethyl-4-bromobutyrate (0.59 ml, 4.21 mmol) was added by syringe and the solution was boiled at reflux. After 53 hr the solvent was evaporated and aq. 10% Na_2CO_3 was added to the residue. Extraction with CH_2Cl_2 (1 x 20 and 3 x 6 ml) gave an oil (584 mg) which was molecularly distilled at 110° (0.005 mm). An additional mol. distillation gave a solid. TLC of a portion of this material (80 mg) on silica gel with ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (2:1) as eluent followed by extraction of the band with R_f 0.4 gave a solid (59 mg). Crystallization from ether gave needles : mp $58.5-59.5^\circ$: λ_{max} 5.58, 5.74, 5.86 μ ; H_δ 1.7—2.15 (m, 2H), 2.2-2.5

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